

GATE Engagement Feedback

Milestone

GATE Engagement Feedback 1

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Introduction to the GATE Community Engagement

After its new [organisational structure](#), the GATE initiative started its community engagement in 2025. As a first step, the GATE team officially invited a small group of research communities to open the GATE to the European Research Area in March 2025.

The GATE initiative launched the new [website](#) and [LinkedIn Social Media](#) on March 17th, 2025, after a meeting with the European Commission's Open Science Team. One day later, they held their first meeting with the European Research Communities to collaborate on bringing the GATE to its fullest potential at the Hanse Office in Brussels. This first meeting was a deliberate attempt to follow a step-by-step approach to fostering (European) capacity-building over the next few years.

Thirty participants attended the hybrid meeting on March 18th 2025, in Brussels.

Summary of the first GATE Community Engagement

The collaborative session and the data from the previously disseminated feedback sheet showed that the 30 representatives are interested in the GATE (Report) for the following:

1. **Trainers:** Individuals defined as trainers, including lecturers at universities or data stewards at repositories, may utilise the GATE report and website to access and contribute to a wealth of shared resources. The GATE report could allow trainers to develop/version their educational materials and share knowledge collaboratively.
2. **Research Community:** Researchers, vice presidents, or other research community representatives at varying expertise levels in open science (OS) can use the GATE report to expand their knowledge and connect with a community of practice. Researchers can also participate in co-creating cutting-edge OS training programs that

The image shows a slide titled "GATE Community Meeting" for the 18th March 2025, 10:00 - 12:00 CET. It is organized by Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel. The slide includes an agenda with sections for Welcome, Programme - Part 1 (10 am - 11 am), and Programme - Part 2 (Needs of the Research Community). It also lists action items for participants. Logos for CAU, GATE, Zenodo, EOSC EU Node, OSF, FORRT, Miller, and NERQ are visible.

GATE Community Meeting
18th March 2025 • 10:00 – 12:00 CET
Christian-Albrechts-Universität Kiel and partners invite you to the **Hanse-Office**, Avenue Palmerston 20, 1000 Brüssel, Belgien, or online.

Agenda

Welcome
We will welcome you at 9.45 am in the lobby of the Hanse-Office. The link to the online access will be sent to you by email.

Programme – Part 1 – 10 am – 11 am
Welcome from the HANSE-OFFICE
Klaas de Boer (Hanse Office)

Welcome from the GATE supporters?
Miller (MIK) & Prof. Dr. Priess-Buchheit (CAU)

About the GATE – Aims, service and engagement towards trustworthy research
Mueller-Karabil (MIK) & Alavi (CAU)

Data Collection, Knowledge Sharing, and Research with the GATE
Prof. Dr. Julia Priess-Buchheit (CAU)

Programme – Part 2 – Needs of the Research Community
We will discuss
1. How can OS trainers work with the GATE?
2. What research community need does the GATE take on?
in breakout sessions (30 minutes).

We will jointly find ideas on how to collaborate in the future (Collaborative Whiteboard).

Action Items
Part 1 – If you are a research community representative, please ensure you have shared your ideas via this [tool](#), before the meeting starts on Tuesday.
Part 2 – We will explain the GATE to you in detail at the meeting. If you want to have a look before the meeting, you can read about its [history](#) and how it works [here](#), see its [service](#), and starting Monday, March 17th, 2025, more information at the GATE's webpage, www.openscienceGATE.com.

are fully open-access. The report allows for targeted training and the cultivation of expertise among basic and experienced users alike.

3. **Policy Makers:** Policymakers might use the GATE report to gauge the impact of evidence-based knowledge dissemination. The GATE report can support policy development by providing access to comprehensive, reliable resources on OS that inform decision-making processes.
4. **Research Funding Organizations (RFOs):** For RFOs, the GATE report is a valuable resource for gathering information necessary to enforce standards for funding applications. It could serve as a reference or 'gold-standard' guide for implementing OS in research projects, ensuring compliance and facilitating better funding practices.
5. **Data Infrastructures:** Professionals involved with data infrastructures might be interested in the GATE report because it has the potential to integrate with existing catalogues, enhance visibility, and perhaps align with initiatives like the EOSC node and EU Data Spaces. GATE could support sharing training practices and resources, aligning metadata models, and fostering collaboration in the data space sector.

The GATE initiative fosters a dynamic ecosystem for professionals across various fields to connect, collaborate, build capacity, and advance knowledge in open science.